

ISic0458

I.Sicily inscription 0458

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 271

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Inho]ç tum[ulo]
2. r, e, q, u, i, e, s[ci]t puel[lano]
3. mine Bon[---][quae]
4. v, i, x, i, t pl(us) m(inus) ann[os ---]

Apparatus

Text of Griesheimer 1989

Translation (en)

In this tomb rests a girl named Bon[... , who] lived more or less [...] years [...?]

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175814

EDCS 21900521

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7180 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650770>)

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Griesheimer, M. 1989. Quelques inscriptions chrétiennes de Sicile orientale. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 65: 143-177. At 150 no.6

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0458. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4337507>